

Disease resistance of some promising rice cultivars

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Bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* and stem rot (SR) caused by *Sclerotium oryzae* are major diseases in nontraditional rice-growing areas of Haryana. We evaluated 30 promising rice cultivars for resistance during 1988 wet season.

To evaluate yield and yield-contributing characters, cultivars were transplanted in 6.2- × 2.0-m plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with three replications. The crop was

fertilized with 120 kg N, 26 kg P, and 5.75 kg Zn/ha. All the P and Zn were applied at puddling; N was applied in three equal splits: at transplanting, 21 d after transplanting (DT), and 42 DT.

To evaluate BB and SR resistance, cultivars were transplanted in two fields, in two 5-m-long rows/entry and an alternate row of susceptible check TN1 for BB and Jhona 349 for SR.

For BB screening, plants were clip-inoculated 45 DT by cutting 5 cm from the tip of the upper leaves with a sickle dipped in bacterial suspension (prepared by soaking small pieces of infected leaves 20 min). SR screening was done in an infected field.

Only six cultivars showed resistance to BB (see table). Seven entries showed resistance to SR.

Susceptibility of promising rice cultivars to BB and SR in Kaul, India, 1988 wet season.

Cultivar	Parentage	Yield (t/ha)	Grain type ^a	Reaction ^b to	
				Bacterial blight	Stem rot
IET8562	IET5122DR9168-13-2	4.9	MS	7	5
IET8950	RP270-36-1-2/Bankura 32	5.0	LS	7	5
IET9247	RPW6-17/ARC6650	5.0	LB	7	5
IET9552	RPW6-17PtB 2	4.1	LB	7	7
IET9553	RPW6-17PtB 2	4.1	LB	7	7
IET9557	RPW6-17PtB 2	4.4	LB	9	9
IET9686	RPW6-17/ARC6650	5.2	LS	7	7
IET9688	RPW6-17/ARC6650	5.1	LB	7	5
IET9700	RPW6-17/ARC6650	4.1	LB	7	1
IET9701	RPW6-17/ARC6650	4.6	LB	7	1
IET9910	ET4141/CR98-7216	5.1	LB	3	7
IET9912	IET4141/CR98-7216	5.4	SB	3	9
IET9924	IRS/Surekha	5.0	SB	7	9
IET9941	Sona/K118	4.4	LB	9	7
IET10294	IR20/CR95-1128	3.5	LS	5	3
IET10301	Phalguna/ARC6650	2.4	LB	7	5
IET10413	CR114/CR115	4.2	MS	3	1
IET10417	CR114/CR115	4.3	LS	5	1
IET10418	CR114/CR115	5.0	LS	3	3
IET10419	CR114/CR115	5.6	MS	7	5
IET10428	IR4219-35-3/IR4570	5.2	LS	7	3
IET10411	CR94/Ratna	5.0	MS	7	7
IET10312	CBII/Ratna	5.9	LS	3	5
IET10313	IR 162/Parmel	5.9	LS	3	7
IET10318	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	6.8	LS	7	5
IET10319	Nam Sagui 19/JR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	4.8	LS	7	9
IET10320	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	4.6	LS	7	9
IET10321	RP6-516-31-6Pusa 33	6.7	LB	5	7
Jaya (check)	RP6-516-31-6Pusa 33	5.5	LB	7	9
PR106 (check)	RP6-516-31-6Pusa 33	5.2	LS	7	7
LSD (0.05)		0.4			
CV (%)		4.9			

^aMS = medium slender, LS = long slender, LB = long bold, SB = short bold. ^bResistant = with score of 3 or below, moderately resistant = score 5, susceptible = score 7 or above.

IET10413 and IET10418 showed resistance to both diseases, but their yields were less than those of the check varieties. IET10318 gave the highest yield, but it is susceptible to BB and only moderately resistant to SR. IET10321 also gave good grain yield, was moderately resistant to BB, and susceptible to SR. Entries IET10321 and IET10313 had good yields and showed resistance to BB. ■

Pest resistance - insects

Reaction of rice cultivars to rice hispa

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Hispa *Dicladispa armigera* (Oliv.) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) recently became a serious pest of rice, occurring in endemic form throughout Assam. Adult bugs scrape parenchymatous tissues off the rice leaves by making parallel streaks; grubs mine between the two epidermal layers inside the leaves. Damaged leaves dry up. Damaged rice plants look like straw. Heavy infestations can extensively damage winter, summer, and autumn rice.

We screened for resistance to hispa, 96 local cultivars suitable for postflood situations for resistance to hispa in early Sep 1987, 1988, and 1989 at Sensowapathar, an endemic area of Sibsagar.

The hispa population peaked (25-38 adults/hill) late Sep to early Oct. Borsali, the local susceptible check, had 100% infestation.

Reaction of rice cultivars to hispa in the field. Sibsagar, Assam, India, 1987-89.

Cultivar	Germplasm reference number	Leaf damage ^a (%)
Malbhog	NS 27	15
Pokikoli	NS 30	17
Silguti	S 307	17
Gajep sali-1	S 100	18
Sarusokua	S 248	20

^a Av of 1987, 1988, and 1989.